

RESEARCH WRITING DIFFICULTIES AND PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN PRACTICAL RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

Using a descriptive-correlational research design, this study is an attempt to determine the relationship between the students' perception on research writing difficulties and their performance in Practical Research. Specifically, it dealt on finding the perceived writing difficulties of 80 senior high school STEM and HUMSS students with regard to the technical aspect and process of research writing through a closed-ended survey questionnaire; evaluating the performance of students in their actual research outputs through researcher-modified holistic and analytic rubrics; and finding the correlation between the students' perceived writing difficulties and their performance in Practical Research using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. The results indicate that the respondents generally agree to have been experiencing difficulties in both the technical aspect that includes research paper format and grammar and sentence construction; as well as in the process of research writing that includes steps in the research process and working on the different parts of the research paper. In addition, the results of the research outputs' evaluation reveal that the students manifest developing skills in their performance in Practical Research. The findings of the study entail that difficulties in both the technical aspect and process of research writing confront the students in the senior high school. While the negative correlation coefficient results indicate that most of the students who have high perceived writing difficulties have low performance in research, the findings show that there is no statistically significant evidence that perceived writing difficulties and performance in Practical Research are correlated. In the light of the findings, the study recommends the need for the assessment of students' difficulties in research writing. Identifying these difficulties can help the Practical Research teachers gauge their students' readiness for academic writing skills, which can have a big impact on the quality of their research outputs. Additionally, more activities and exercises may be provided by research teachers to help students improve their performance in Practical Research, particularly in the areas of content and focus, sources and format, and conventions. These activities could take the form of courses and modules that focus on note-taking, summarizing, and paraphrasing, all of which are critical skills in research writing. More so, the number of research teacher training programs may be increased to help teachers deal with students' research writing problems and other research-writing concerns.

Keywords: academic writing, research-writing difficulties and performance in research, descriptive-correlational research design, Philippines